

DESCRIPTION OF MODERN CONCEPTS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the analysis of psychological theories of emotional intelligence. The article also covers issues such as the study of emotional intelligence in Russian psychology and the analysis of foreign psychologists, the description of modern concepts of emotional intelligence, the interrelation of intellectual and affective experiences.*

Keywords: *emotional, emotional intelligence, affect, communication, personality, cognitive processes, emotional consciousness, regulation, emotion control, communication perception, ability, thinking, interpersonal relationships, social perception.*

Currently, the concept of emotional intelligence attracts many researchers, so it turned out that the presence of high intelligence does not provide the owner with success in life, does not make him happy. Emotions are important in decision making, in interpersonal relationships, so it is reasonable to assume that in addition to high cognitive abilities, something else is important.

According to I.N. Andreeva, emotional intelligence is the ability to be attentive to the emotional part of one's personality, the ability to track one's emotions and understand what they're talking about, a person who understands his feelings will naturally be happier. Success and happiness in all areas of life are determined by the awareness of their emotions and the ability to cope with their feelings [1,58].

Since the beginning of the twentieth century, psychology has been searching for abilities that, in contrast to the traditionally distinguished general intellect, are associated with the socio-emotional sphere of the psyche. Leading experts in the field of the psychology of intelligence, including social intelligence E. Torndike, C. Spearman, D. Wexler, J. Guildford, G. Eisenk and others argued that people differ in their ability to understand other people and manage to still act reasonably in human relations [2, 97].

In Russian psychology, the idea of the unity of affect and intellect was reflected in the works of L.S. Vygotsky, L.S. Rubinshtein and A.N. Leontiev. L.S. Vygotsky came to the conclusion that there is a dynamic semantic system, which is the unity of affective and intellectual processes: "As you know, the separation of the intellectual side of our consciousness from its affective, volitional side represents one of the main and root defects of all traditional psychology. In this case, thinking inevitably turns into an autonomous flow of thinking thoughts, it breaks away from the fullness of living life ... " The unity of affect and intellect, according to L.S. Vygotsky, is found, firstly, in the interconnection and mutual influence of these sides of the psyche at all stages of development, and secondly, in the fact that this connection is dynamic, and of any level in the development of thinking corresponds to its own stage in the development of affect [3,157]. S.L. Rubinshtein, developing the ideas of L.S. Vygotsky, noted that thinking in itself is a unity of the emotional and rational. However, the approaches outlined by L. S. Vygotsky to understanding the unity of affect and intellect in the process of human development were not properly developed at the time [4,125].

H. Gardner came up especially close to the concept of emotional intelligence, who, within the framework of personal intelligence, distinguished between intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence. The abilities included by him in these concepts are directly related to emotional intelligence. So, inside, personal intelligence is interpreted by him as “access to one’s own emotional life, to one’s affects and emotions: the ability to instantly distinguish feelings, call them, translate into symbolic codes and use them as means for understanding and controlling one’s own behavior” [5, 96] .

In 1988, Ruven Bar-He introduced the concept of emotional-social intelligence and suggested that it consists of many, both deeply personal and interpersonal abilities, skills and abilities, which, when combined, determine the behavior of a person. Bar-He first introduced the designation EQ - emotional quotient, coefficient of emotionality, by analogy with IQ - coefficient of intelligence [6, 33].

In turn, K. Saarni in 1990 examined the concept of emotional competence and included eight interrelated emotional and social skills in it [7,14].

More and more works devoted to abilities in the social and emotional field began to appear in scientific and popular literature, so many new facts were obtained and so many new theoretical developments were carried out that, as C. Isard noted, one could rightly speak of a coup in this area [8.45].

In addition, the problem of identifying and understanding emotions was dealt not only with psychologists, but also with specialists in other sciences — evolutionary biologists, psychiatrists, programmers, etc., who revealed many human abilities in this field of research. In order to avoid discrepancies in the study of the problem of identification and understanding of emotions by a person, American psychologists P. Solovey, J. Meyer in 1990 proposed that these abilities constitute a unitary concept - “emotional intelligence”. The authors themselves consider emotional intelligence as a substructure of social intelligence, which includes the ability to track their own and other people's feelings and emotions, distinguish between them and use this information to guide thinking and action. The same scientists developed the first and most famous model of emotional intelligence in scientific psychology. This is a complex construct consisting of three types of abilities:

1. Identification and expression of emotions;
2. Regulation of emotions;
3. The use of emotional information in thinking and activity [9,2].

In the context of this justification, emotional intelligence is interpreted as the ability to process the information contained in emotions: to determine the meaning of emotions, their relationship with each other, to use emotional information as the basis for thinking and decision making. These components are arranged in a hierarchy whose levels, according to the authors, are assimilated sequentially in ontogenesis. Each component concerns both one’s own emotions and the emotions of other people.

According to D.V. Lyusin, emotional intelligence includes the following mental abilities:

1. The ability to accurately perceive, evaluate and express emotions;
2. The ability to have access and evoke feelings in order to increase the effectiveness of thinking;
3. The ability to understand emotions, emotional knowledge;

4. The ability to consciously regulate emotions, manage emotions, increase the level of emotional and intellectual development [10, 29].

Abilities - which appear relatively early in the course of personality development, are on the left side of the branches, and abilities that develop later - on the right.

Since early skills are associated with development (left) are usually poorly combined with each other, they most clearly illustrate the differences among the branches. Abilities developing at a later time (on the right) appear in the more integrated personality of an adult and, therefore, are less distinct. Each ability relates to emotions in relation to itself and others, except as otherwise noted. It is assumed that people with a higher emotional intelligence will go through the indicated steps faster and show a greater number of these abilities:

1. Perception - the assessment and expression of emotions with which people can distinguish emotions, identify emotional content. This is the initial, basic component related to non-verbal perception and expression of emotion. The expressions of persons representing happiness, sadness, anger and fear are universal for recognizing these emotions in all people. Infants and young children learn to identify their own and others' emotional states and to distinguish them from each other. First, the infant distinguishes the emotional expressions of the face of the parent and responds to them. With age, the child more accurately identifies his own muscular and physical sensations and the environment. A mature person can carefully control their inner feelings. The ability to accurately perceive the emotions displayed on the face or voice of another person provides a crucial starting point for a more subtle understanding of emotions.

2. Use of emotions to increase the effectiveness of thinking - This component is as fundamental as the first. It reflects the ability of emotions to orient the cognitive system and promote thinking. It includes the ability to use emotions to direct attention to important events, to evoke emotions that contribute to solving problems. For example, a positive attitude is involved in the implementation of creative thought, and mood swings can be used as a means of analyzing different points of view on a problem.

3. Understanding emotions - Emotions convey information: happiness usually indicates a desire to unite with other people; anger indicates a desire to attack or harm others; fear indicates a desire to escape, etc. Each emotion conveys its own pattern of possible messages and actions related to these messages. Anger, for example, can be associated with certain sets of possible actions: peacekeeping, assault, retaliation, and seeking revenge. Understanding the emotional messages and actions associated with them is one important aspect of this area of skill. As soon as a person can identify such messages and potential actions, the ability to reason about emotional messages and actions becomes also important. In other words, a full understanding of emotions evokes an understanding of the meaning of emotions, coupled with the ability to reason about these meanings. This is an important point regarding this group of emotional and intellectual skills.

4. Managing emotions - Emotions can often be controlled. A person must understand that emotions convey information. Within certain limits, when emotions are under control, a person can be open to a wide variety of emotional signals - until the most powerful, suppressing others appear.

Thus, the ability to recognize and express emotions is a necessary basis for generating emotions in order to solve specific problems. These two abilities are procedural in nature.

In the 1990s, other models appeared that represented a slightly different view of emotional intelligence. The most famous are the models of D. Goleman and R. Bar-On.

In 1995, D. Goleman changed and popularized the first model of emotional intelligence by J. Meyer and P. Solovey to their selected components. D. Goleman added a few more - enthusiasm, perseverance and social skills. Thus, he combined the cognitive abilities that were part of the Solovey and Meyer model with personal characteristics. Due to the popularity of Goleman's book "Emotional Intelligence", first published in 1995, his model gained great fame not only among psychologists, but also in wider circles. Later D. Goleman finalized the structure of emotional intelligence [11,78]:

1. Self-control;
2. Control of emotions - the ability to control destructive emotions and impulses;
3. Openness - a manifestation of honesty and directness, reliability;
4. Adaptability - flexible adaptation to a changing situation and overcoming obstacles;
5. The will to win is a persistent desire to improve productivity in order to meet internal quality standards;
6. Initiative - willingness to take action and the ability not to miss an opportunity;
7. Optimism - the ability to look positively at things.
8. Social skills - these abilities determine how we manage our relationships with people;
9. Social sensitivity;
10. Empathy - the ability to listen to the feelings of other people, an understanding of their position and an active manifestation of a sympathetic attitude to their problems.
11. Business awareness - an understanding of current events, hierarchies of responsibility and policies at the organizational level.
12. Courtesy - the ability to recognize and satisfy the needs of subordinates, customers or customers;
13. Relationship management;
14. Inspiration - the ability to lead, drawing an exciting picture of the future;
15. Influence - possession of a number of persuasion tactics;
16. Assistance in self-improvement: encouraging the development of the abilities of other people through feedback and guidance;
17. Promoting change - the ability to initiate change, improve management practices and lead workers in a new direction;
18. Conflict Resolution - Dispute Resolution.
19. Strengthening personal relationships: cultivating and maintaining social ties;
20. Teamwork and cooperation - interaction with other employees and team building.

The undoubted merit of D. Goleman is to stimulate people to develop personal qualities that contribute to the achievement of success in certain fields of activity. Nevertheless, it is obvious that among the structural components of emotional intelligence distinguished by Goleman, one can find not only emotional abilities, but also volitional qualities, characteristics of self-awareness, social skills.

In 2004, Russian psychologist D.V. Lyusin also proposed a fundamentally new model of emotional intelligence. The author defines emotional intelligence as the ability to understand and control his own and others' emotions. Under the ability to understand and control emotions, D. V. Lyusin understands the following [12,129]:

1. The ability to understand emotions means that a person can recognize an emotion, also establish the fact of having an emotional experience in himself or in another person;

2. Emotion, also establish what kind of emotion he or another person experiences, and find verbal expression for it;

3. Understands the causes that caused this emotion, and the consequences to which it will lead;

4. The ability to manage emotions means that a person can control the intensity of emotions, primarily muffle excessively strong emotions, can control the external expression of emotions, and, if necessary, arbitrarily cause one or another emotion.

5. The ability to understand, and the ability to manage emotions can be directed both at our own emotions and at the emotions of other people, that is, we can talk about both intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional intelligence. These two options suggest the actualization of different cognitive processes and skills, but should be related to each other.

An analysis of the theoretical views of the above authors allows us to determine emotional intelligence as a set of emotional and cognitive abilities for socio-psychological adaptation of a person. People with a high level of development of emotional intelligence have expressed abilities to understand their own emotions and the emotions of other people, they can control their emotional sphere, which determines their higher adaptability and effectiveness in communication, they more easily achieve their goals in interaction with others.

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